

Science

THE COMMUTATIVITY OF PRIME NEAR RINGS

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Abstract

Let N be a near-ring, and σ be an automorphisms of N . An additive mapping d from a near-ring N into itself is called a reverse σ -derivation on N if $d(xy) = d(y)x + \sigma(y)d(x)$, holds for all $x, y \in N$. In this paper, we shall investigate the commutativity of N by a reverse σ -derivation d satisfied some properties, when N is a prime ring.

Keywords: Prime Near Ring; Reverse Derivation; Reverse Σ -Derivation; Commutativity.

Mathematics Subject Classification: 16W25, 16Y30, 16U80.

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1. Introduction

Near-rings are one of the generalize structures of rings. A near-ring N is a ring $(N, +, \cdot)$, where $+$ is not necessarily abelian and with only one distributive law. A left near-ring (resp. right near-ring) is called a zero-symmetric left near-ring (resp. a zero-symmetric right near-ring) if $0x = 0$ (resp. $x0 = 0$), for all $x \in N$. A near-ring N called a prime near-ring if $xNy = 0$ implies $x = 0$ or $y = 0$, for all $x, y \in N$. The multiplicative center Z of N will denote, $Z = \{ x \in N: xy = yx \text{ for all } y \in N \}$. The symbol $[x, y]$ will denote the commutator $xy - yx$, for all $x, y \in N$, and note that important identities $[x, yz] = y[x, z] + [x, y]z$ and $[xy, z] = x[y, z] + [x, z]y$ satisfied for all $x, y, z \in N$. An additive mapping $d: N \rightarrow N$ is called derivation if $d(xy) = xd(y) + d(x)y$, or equivalently (cf.[7]) that $d(xy) = d(x)y + xd(y)$, for all $x, y \in N$. The derivation d will called commuting if $[d(x), x] = 0$, for all $x \in N$. The study of commutativity of prime near-rings by using derivations was initiated by H. E. Bell and G. Mason in 1987 [2], and Yilun Shang [8] satisfying the commutativity of prime near rings N if there exist $k, l \in N$ such that N admits a generalized derivation D satisfying either $D([x, y]) = k[x, y]l$ for all $x, y \in N$ or $D([x, y]) = -k[x, y]l$ for all $x, y \in N$. In [5] A. A. M. Kamal generalizes some results of Bell and Mason by studying the commutativity of 3-prime near-rings using a σ -derivation instead of the usual derivation, where σ is an automorphism on the near-ring. Bresar and Vukman in 1989 [3] have introduced the notion of a reverse derivation as an additive mapping d from a ring R into itself satisfying $d(xy) = d(y)x + yd(x)$, for all $x, y \in R$. Samman and Alyamani [6] studied the reverse derivations on semi prime

rings. C.Jaya S. R., G.Venkata B.Rao and S.Vasantha Kumar in [4] studied generalized reverse derivation of a semi prime ring R and proved that if f is a generalized reverse derivation with a derivation d , then f is a strong commutativity preserving and R is commutative. Afrah M.Ibraheem in [1] used the notion of reverse derivations on a prime Γ -near ring M to study the commutativity conditions of M , when U be a non-zero invariant subset of M . In this paper, we shall prove that a prime near-ring which admits a nonzero reverse σ -derivation satisfying certain conditions must be a commutative ring. Throughout the paper N will denote a zero symmetric near-ring with multiplicative center Z .

2. Preliminary Results

To prove our results we start with the following definition and lemmas:

Definition 2.1:

Let N be a near-ring, and σ is an automorphism on N . An additive mapping d from N into itself is called a reverse σ -derivation on N if satisfying $d(xy) = d(y)x + \sigma(y)d(x)$, for all $x, y \in N$.

Lemma 2.2:

Let d be an arbitrary additive automorphism of N . Then $d(xy) = \sigma(y)d(x) + d(y)x$ for all $x, y \in N$ if and only if $d(xy) = d(y)x + \sigma(y)d(x)$, for all $x, y \in N$. Therefore d is a reverse σ -derivation if and only if $d(xy) = d(y)x + \sigma(y)d(x)$.

Proof: Suppose

$$d(xy) = \sigma(y)d(x) + d(y)x,$$

for all $x, y \in N$. Since

$$(x+x)y = xy + xy,$$

$$d((x+x)y) = d(xy + xy)$$

$$d((x+x)y) = \sigma(y)d(x+x) + d(y)(x+x).$$

$$= \sigma(y)d(x) + \sigma(y)d(x) + d(y)x + d(y)x \dots \tag{1},$$

for all $x, y \in N$. And,

$$d(xy+xy) = d(xy) + d(xy)$$

$$= \sigma(y)d(x) + d(y)x + \sigma(y)d(x) + d(y)x \dots \tag{2},$$

for all $x, y \in N$. From (1) and (2), we get

$$\sigma(y)d(x) + d(y)x = d(y)x + \sigma(y)d(x),$$

So,

$$d(xy) = d(y)x + \sigma(y)d(x),$$

for all $x, y \in N$. The converse is similarly.

Lemma 2.3:

Let N be a prime near-ring, and d be a nonzero reverse σ -derivation of N . If $d(N) \subset Z(N)$ then N is a commutative ring.

Proof

Let $d(x) \in Z(N)$, for all $x \in N$. Then

$$d(x)z = zd(x) \dots \quad (1)$$

Replacing x by xy in (1), we have

$$(d(y)x + \sigma(y)d(x))z = z(d(y)x + \sigma(y)d(x)),$$

Then

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma(y)d(x)z - z\sigma(y)d(x) &= -d(y)xz + zd(y)x, \\ &= -d(y)xz + d(y)zx \dots \end{aligned} \quad (2),$$

for all $x, y \in N$. Replacing $\sigma(y)$ by $d(x)$ in (2) and using (1), we get

$$\begin{aligned} d(y)(-xz + zx) &= d(y)[-x, z] \\ &= d(y)[z, x] = 0 \dots \end{aligned} \quad (3),$$

for all $x, y, z \in N$. Replacing z by zy in (3) and using (3) again, we get
 $d(y)z[y, x] = 0$,

for all $x, y, z \in N$. Since N is a prime, and $d \neq 0$, we have

$$[y, x] = 0,$$

for all $x, y \in N$. Therefore N is commutative.

Lemma 2.4:

Let N be a prime near-ring with center Z , and let d be a nonzero reverse σ -derivation of N , then $d(Z) \subset Z$.

Proof: For any $z \in Z$ and $x \in N$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} d(xz) &= d(zx). \\ d(xz) &= d(z)x + \sigma(z)d(x) \\ &= \sigma(z)d(x) + d(z)x, \end{aligned}$$

by lemma 2.2. If we replace $\sigma(z)$ by z , we get

$$d(xz) = zd(x) + d(z)x \dots \quad (1),$$

for all $x, z \in N$.

$$d(zx) = d(x)z + \sigma(x)d(z) \dots \quad (2),$$

for all $x, z \in N$. From (1) and (2), we get

$$d(z)x = \sigma(x)d(z),$$

and since σ is automorphism, we have
 $d(z)x = xd(z)$,

for all $x, z \in N$, Therefore $d(z) \in Z$, this complete proof.

Lemma 2.5:

Let d be a nonzero reverse σ -derivation of a prime near-ring N , and $x \in N$.
If $xd(N) = 0$ or $d(N)x = 0$, then $x = 0$.

Proof: Let assume that,

$$x d(n) = 0 \dots \tag{1},$$

for all $n \in N$. Replacing n by mn in (1), we have

$$x d(n)m + x \sigma(n)d(m) = 0 \dots \tag{2},$$

for all $x, n, m \in N$. By using (1) in (2), and since σ is automorphism, we have
 $x N d(m) = 0$,

for all $x, m \in N$, and since N is a prime, and $d(N) \neq 0$, we have $x = 0$.
Similarly, we can prove $x = 0$, if $d(N)x = 0$.

3. The Commutativity of Prime Near Ring N

In this section we give conditions under which a prime near ring N must be commutative ring.

Theorem 3.1:

For a prime near ring N , let d be a nonzero reverse σ -derivation of N , such that $[x, d(x)] = 0$, for all $x \in N$, then N is commutative.

Proof: Let

$$[x, d(x)] = 0 \dots \tag{1},$$

for all $x \in N$. Replacing $d(x)$ by $yd(x)$ in (1) and using (1) again, we have

$$[x, y] d(x) = 0 \dots \tag{2},$$

for all $x, y \in N$. Replace y by zy in equ.(2) and using (2), we get,

$$[x, z] y d(x) = 0,$$

for all $x, y, z \in N$. Since N is a prime, we have either $[x, z] = 0$ or $d(x) = 0$.

Since $d(x) \neq 0$, for all $x \in N$, then we have $[x, z] = 0$, it follows that $x \in Z(N)$ for each fixed $x \in N$, and by lemma 2.4, we get $d(x) \in Z(N)$, that's $d(N) \subset Z(N)$. Then by lemma 2.3, we get N is commutative.

Theorem 3.2:

Let N be a prime near ring, and d be a nonzero reverse σ -derivation of N . If $[d(y), d(x)] = 0$, for all $x, y \in N$, then N is commutative.

Proof: Given that

$$[d(y), d(x)] = 0 \dots \tag{1}$$

for all $x, y \in N$. Replacing y by yx in (1), we get,
 $[d(x)y + \sigma(x)d(y), d(x)] = 0$,

By using (1) again, we get
 $d(x)[y, d(x)] + [\sigma(x), d(x)]d(y) = 0 \dots \tag{2}$

for all $x, y \in N$. Replacing y by zy , where $z \in Z(N)$ in equ.(2), we get,

$$d(x)z[y, d(x)] + d(x)[z, d(x)]y + [\sigma(x), d(x)]d(y)z + [\sigma(x), d(x)]\sigma(y)d(z) = 0 \dots \tag{3}$$

for all $x, y, z \in N$. Since σ is automorphism, and by using (2) in (3), we get
 $[\sigma(x), d(x)]y d(z) = 0$,

for all $x, y, z \in N$. Since N is a prime, we have either
 $[\sigma(x), d(x)] = 0$, or $d(z) = 0$.

Since $d(z) \neq 0$, we have
 $[\sigma(x), d(x)] = 0 \dots \tag{4}$

for all $x \in N$. Replacing $\sigma(x)$ by x in (4), and by using the similar procedure as in Theorem 3.1, we get, N is commutative.

Theorem 3.3:

Let N be a prime near ring, and d be a nonzero reverse σ -derivation of N . If $[x, d(y)] \in Z(N)$, for all $x, y \in N$, then N is commutative.

Proof: Assume that

$$[x, d(y)] \in Z(N),$$

for all $x, y \in N$. Hence for all $n \in N$,
 $[[x, d(y)], n] = 0 \dots \tag{1}$

Replacing x by $xd(y)$ in (1), and using (1) again, we get
 $[x, d(y)][d(y), n] = 0 \dots \tag{2}$

for all $x, y, n \in N$.

Replacing x by nx in (2), and using (2) again, we get
 $[n, d(y)] x [d(y), n] = 0...$ (3),

for all $x, y, n \in N$. Since N is a prime, we have either
 $[n, d(y)] = 0...$ (4),

for all $y, n \in N$, or
 $[d(y), n] = 0...$ (5),

for all $y, n \in N$. If we replacing $d(y)$ by $md(y)$ in (4) and (5), and using them again, we get
 $[n, m] d(y) = 0$

or $[m, n] d(y) = 0$,

for all $y, n, m \in N$. By using lemma 2.5 in two cases, we have

$$[n, m] = 0, \text{ and } [m, n] = 0,$$

for all $n, m \in N$. Therefore, N is commutative.

Theorem 3.4:

Let N be a prime near ring, d be a nonzero reverse σ -derivation of N , and $y \in N$. If $[d(x), y] = 0$ then $d(y) = 0$ or $y \in Z(N)$.

Proof: Let

$$[x, d(x)] = 0... \quad (1),$$

for all $x \in N$. Replacing $d(x)$ by $yd(x)$ in (1) and using (1) again, we have
 $[x, y] d(x) = 0...$ (2),

For all $x, y \in N$. Replace y by zy in equ.(2) and using (2), we get,
 $[x, z] y d(x) = 0$,

For all $x, y, z \in N$. Since N is a prime, we have either
 $[x, z] = 0$ or $d(x) = 0$.

Since $d(x) \neq 0$, for all $x \in N$, then we have $[x, z] = 0$, it follows that $x \in Z(N)$ for each fixed $x \in N$, and by lemma 2.4, we get $d(x) \in Z(N)$, that's $d(N) \subset Z(N)$. Then by lemma 2.3, we get N is commutative.

Theorem 3.5:

Let N be a prime near ring, and d be a nonzero reverse σ -derivation of N , such that
 $d([x, y]) = [x, d(y)]$, for all $x, y \in N$, then N is commutative.

Proof: Given that

$$d([x, y]) = [x, d(y)] \dots \quad (1),$$

for all $x, y \in N$. Replacing y by yx in (1) and using (1), we get,

$$[x, d(x)]y + [x, \sigma(x)]d(y) = 0 \dots \quad (2),$$

for all $x, y \in N$. If we replacing $\sigma(x)$ by x in (2), we have

$$[x, d(x)]y = 0 \dots \quad (3),$$

for all $x, y \in N$. Replacing y by $yd(x)$ in (3), we get

$$[x, d(x)]y d(x) = 0,$$

for all $x, y \in N$. Since N is a prime, and $d \neq 0$, we have

$$[x, d(x)] = 0,$$

for all $x \in N$. Then by theorem 3.1, we get, N is commutative.

4. Conclusions

For an automorphism σ on a near ring N , we study the commutativity on N , if N has a non zero reverse σ -derivation d , where d is defined as an additive mapping from N into itself satisfying $d(xy) = d(y)x + \sigma(y)d(x)$, for all $x, y \in N$, and introduced some conditions on d to get the commutativity on N when N is a prime near ring.

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References

- [1] M. Afrah Ibraheem, (2015). "Reverse Derivations on Prime Gamma Near Rings", Int. J. Pure Appl. Sci. Technol., 26(2), 64-69.
- [2] H. E. Bell and G. Mason, (1987). "On derivations in near-rings, Near-rings and near-fields (Tubingen, 1985)", North-Holland Math. Stud., 137, North-Holland, Amsterdam, 31-35.
- [3] M. Bresar and J. Vukman, (1989). "On some additive mappings in rings with involution", A equations math., 38, 178-185.
- [4] C.Jaya Subba Reddy, G. Venkata Bhaskara Rao, S.Vasantha Kumar, (2015). "Generalized Reverse Derivations on Semi prime Rings", The Bulletin of Society for Mathematical Services, Vol. 15, 1-4.
- [5] A. A. M. Kamal, (2001). " σ -derivations on prime near-rings", Tamkang J. Math. 32, 89-93.
- [6] M. Samman, N. Alyamani, (2007). "Derivations and reverse derivations in semi prime rings", International Mathematical, Forum, 2, No. 39, 1895-1902.
- [7] X. K.Wang, (1994). "Derivations in prime near-rings", Proc. Amer. Math. Soc., 121(2), 361-366.
- [8] Yilun Shang, (2015). "A Note on the Commutativity of Prime Near-rings", Algebra Colloquium, 22(3), 361-366.

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